

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Simulation model for heat stress scenarios

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry
Flagship project FORMIDABILÆ
RM4- UNISS CONTRIBUTION

DELIVERABLE D4.2

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	29/09/2025	Final version	Prof. Alberto Stanislao Atzori

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Table of Contents

GLOSSARY.....	3
A) HEAT STRESS SCENARIO MODEL	4
INTRODUCTION	4
MATERIALS AND METHODS.....	4
RESULTS.....	5
REFERENCES	7
B) DATA-DRIVEN PREDICTION OF MILK PRODUCTION SCENARIOS: A DEEP LEARNING APP.....	8
C) DEVELOPMENT OF HEAT GUARD, A WEB AND ANDROID-BASED APPLICATION FOR MONITORING AND PREDICTING HEAT STRESS IN DAIRY CATTLE	10
D) DEVELOPMENT OF THE HEAT GUARD CHATBOT USING ZEPHYR.....	14

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Heat stress scenario model

Introduction

The aim of this study is to predict daily milk yield under scenarios of whole summer conditions using a set of variables including the same-day heat stress index (THI) and short-term time windows (3- and 7-day averages and the previous day's value), short-term milk production history (the previous day's value and the 3-day average), and animal-based variables (lactation stage and parity group). For this purpose, a linear regression model and several machine learning algorithms (Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting, and Gradient Boosting Machine) were used to investigate the possibility of nonlinear or threshold patterns in addition to linear relationships, based on THI scenarios.

Materials and methods

Data collection

To predict milk yield during the summer in dairy cows, data from three commercial farms located in Arborea (Italy) were used; both farms were equipped with automated milking systems (AMS), and for each cow, daily data including days in milk (DIM), parity, and daily milk yield were recorded during the whole summer period of 1 July to 30 September 2022.

From the initial dataset, only records from cows with parity numbers 1–5 were selected, and cows with parity numbers ≥ 6 were excluded. Also, cows with DIM greater than 350 at the beginning of July were excluded from the study. Data cleaning was performed in several steps. First, all cows with any daily milk yield below 10 kg were excluded. Second, for each cow, the mean and standard deviation of daily milk yield were calculated across the observation period, and if even one record was more than three standard deviations away from the cow's mean, all records of that cow were excluded from the analysis to avoid the influence of abnormal values and potential data entry errors. The cows under study were divided into two groups based on parity: primiparous (parity = 1) and multiparous (parity ≥ 2). Based on DIM, the lactation stage of each cow was divided into three categories: early lactation (DIM ≤ 100), mid lactation (101 \leq DIM \leq 200), and late lactation (DIM > 200).

Recording and calculation of environmental data

During summer 2022, environmental data on dry-bulb temperature (Tdb) and relative humidity (RH) were recorded hourly at each farm by dedicated data loggers from 1 July to 30 September. The temperature–humidity index (THI) was calculated based on the following equation proposed by the National Research Council:

$$\text{THI} = [(1.8 \times \text{Tdb} + 32) - (0.55 - (0.0055 \times \text{RH})) \times (1.8 \times \text{Tdb} - 26)] \quad (1)$$

where Tdb is the dry-bulb temperature (in degrees Celsius) and RH is the relative humidity (in percent). The daily mean THI for each farm was then obtained and used in the analyses.

Model development

The study was conducted in two steps: (1) internal validation using data from two farms and (2) external validation on an independent farm. The purpose of external validation was to assess the generalizability of the model to “unseen” cows and to avoid overfitting.

The dataset included daily milk yield, summer heat stress index (THI), DIM, cow identifier, and farm. For each cow, time-based, leak-free features were constructed from the past only: previous day’s production (Milk lag 1), 3-day rolling average of production (Milk roll 3), previous day’s THI (THI lag 1), 3-day rolling average of THI (THI roll 3), and 7-day rolling average of THI (THI roll 7). Group variables included parity group (Primiparous; Multiparous) and lactation stage based on DIM (Early: ≤ 100 days; Mid: 101–200; Late: > 200).

The GLM (Linear model) was fitted with the above inputs; as a comparison, three machine learning algorithms, Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) were used to investigate potential nonlinear or threshold relationships in the data. In the internal validation step, cow-wise 80/20 splits were used repeatedly to ensure that each cow’s records were placed in only one of the two sets (training or testing). Evaluation criteria included R^2 (coefficient of determination), RMSE (root mean square error), and CCC (Lin’s concordance correlation coefficient). Finally, in the external validation step, the fitted models were fully evaluated on the Panetto farm without any retraining. Analyses were performed in RStudio with the packages corresponding to each model and algorithm and for plotting.

Results

The internal evaluation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models are presented in Table 1. In this set, GBM showed the best performance (Figure 1-B), achieving the lowest RMSE (4.828) and the highest R^2 (0.740) and CCC (0.850). The XGB and GLM algorithms performed very similarly and slightly worse than GBM (XGB: RMSE = 4.859, R^2 = 0.736, CCC = 0.847; GLM: RMSE = 4.897, R^2 = 0.732, CCC = 0.845), and RF provided the lowest accuracy in this evaluation (R^2 = 0.725; RMSE = 4.960; CCC = 0.837).

Table 1. Internal cross-validation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models¹

Model	R^2	RMSE	CCC
GLM	0.732	4.897	0.845
GBM	0.740	4.828	0.850
XGB	0.736	4.859	0.847
RF	0.725	4.960	0.837

¹ GLM, General linear model with fixed effects; GBM, Gradient boosting machine; XGB, Extreme gradient boosting; RF, Random forest; R^2 , Coefficient of determination; RMSE, Root mean square error; CCC: Lin’s concordance correlation coefficient

Figure 1. Observed vs. Predicted Milk Yield: (A) GLM, (B) GBM, (C) XGB, (D) RF.

The external validation results for the GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF models are shown in Table 2. GLM performed best, achieving the lowest RMSE (1.028) and the highest R^2 (0.981) and CCC (0.990). Compared with the closest machine-learning algorithms, the RMSE was about 0.22 lower (vs XGB at 1.252). XGB and RF performed very similarly, with GBM slightly weaker than both ($R^2 = 0.969$; RMSE = 1.314; CCC = 0.984). Unlike the internal evaluation, the ranking of the machine-learning algorithms in the external validation was not exactly replicated; nevertheless, GLM remained the most stable and accurate model.

Table 2. External validation (farm-out) results for GLM, GBM, XGB, and RF¹

Model	R^2	RMSE	CCC
GLM	0.981	1.028	0.990
GBM	0.969	1.314	0.984
XGB	0.972	1.252	0.986
RF	0.972	1.265	0.986

¹ GLM, General linear model with fixed effects; GBM, Gradient boosting machine; XGB, Extreme gradient boosting; RF, Random forest; R^2 , Coefficient of determination; RMSE, Root mean square error; CCC: Lin's concordance correlation coefficient

In the internal evaluation, although GBM was slightly better than the others and XGB and GLM performed very close and slightly weaker, in the external validation where stability and

generalizability are measured, GLM was the best by a significant margin and achieved RMSE about 0.22 units lower than the closest machine learning algorithm, XGB. XGB and RF were almost similar, and GBM appeared slightly weaker than them. This inversion of the ranking between internal and external evaluations suggests that GBM's internal superiority is likely due to overfitting to the training farm patterns, while the simple GLM structure relying on the short-term autoregressive components of milk, the incremental effect of THI, and the two group variables parity and lactation stage provided higher generalizability to the independent farm due to the nearly linear relationships and the absence of strong interactions. In other words, when the data are low in nonlinearity, the advantage of complex structures is lost, leaving GLM as the most stable and accurate option for prediction.

References

- Becker, C. A., Collier, R. J., & Stone, A. E. (2020). Invited review: Physiological and behavioral effects of heat stress in dairy cows. *Journal of dairy science*, 103(8), 6751-6770.
- Giannone, C., Bovo, M., Ceccarelli, M., Torreggiani, D., & Tassinari, P. (2023). Review of the heat stress-induced responses in dairy cattle. *Animals*, 13(22), 3451.
- Nascimento, B. M., Gaddis, K. L. P., Koltes, J. E., Tempelman, R. J., VandeHaar, M. J., White, H. M., ... & Weigel, K. A. (2025). Impact of heat stress on dry matter intake and residual feed intake in mid-lactation dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 108(7), 7345-7353.

B) Data-Driven Prediction of Milk Production scenarios: A Deep Learning App

Recent advances in data science have opened new opportunities for the development of dynamic, high-resolution predictive models that incorporate animal-specific, environmental, and temporal factors. The main aim was to evaluate the performance of a deep learning-based system for predicting daily milk production in dairy cows. 203,321 individual daily observations were gathered from six farms from July to January. Variables: daily milk production, days in lactation, number of lactations, number and type of milkings (complete/incomplete or interrupted), feed intake, temperature and humidity index (THI). Modelling: Forecasting pipe was developed in collaboration with the Department of Mathematics and Computer Science, Università di Cagliari, Via Ospedale 72, 09124 Cagliari, Italy within the PNRR “COMPUDAMOS” of the PNRR E.Ins –Ecosystem of Innovation for Next Generation Sardinia and is presented in Figure 1. Cows were grouped according to their production patterns using TimeSeries K-Means with Dynamic Time Warping as the distance metric. For each cluster, a separate Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network was trained to predict the next day's milk production using a window of 7 days prior to the production day. Each LSTM model was trained using 64 hidden units and optimized to minimize the MSE on the validation set. Performance was evaluated on test sets excluded.

Results and implications: The proposed system has shown promising results in predicting daily milk production, especially during heat waves (Figure 2). TimeSeries K-Means clustering identified four distinct groups of cows based on their lactation time series patterns. Predictive accuracy of mean square error (RMSE) values ranging from 4.12 kg/d (Cluster 1) to 5.16 kg/d (Cluster 3) (Table 1). Dynamic clustering allowed the model to adapt to different production profiles, improving its flexibility and generalization. The integration of environmental data (THI) and animal variables (e.g., number of incomplete milkings, feed intake) contributed to the robustness of the model. The data-driven approach proved capable of learning complex and non-linear relationships without predefined assumptions, offering a viable alternative to traditional empirical models. Deep learning-based forecasting systems can support decisions in dairy farming, particularly if combined with automated data collection systems. LSTM networks, in accurately predicted daily milk production in dairy cows using real data from farms. Grouping animals based on production patterns improved the accuracy and adaptability of the model. Future developments should focus on the robustness of predictions through extended datasets and continuous retraining of the model with new incoming data for broader applications across animal species and farming systems.

Table 1. Dataset evaluation.

Cluster	# Cows	# Temporal Series	MSE (Kg ²)	RMSE (Kg)	MAE (Kg)
0	212	53585	17.01	4.12	2.57
1	393	45235	6.76	2.60	1.38
2	119	36377	26.67	5.16	3.55
3	179	50986	23.82	4.88	2.97

Figure 1. Forecasting model pipeline.

Figure 2. Scenario of Milk production forecast vs. observed values.

C) Development of Heat Guard, a Web and Android-Based Application for Monitoring and Predicting Heat Stress in Dairy Cattle

Importance of Heat Stress Monitoring in Dairy Cattle Management

Regular monitoring of heat stress allows dairy farm managers to prevent declines in milk production, reduced fertility, increased disease incidence, and economic losses. Monitoring thermal indices and climatic conditions supports faster decision-making regarding management strategies, such as ventilation, feeding, milking, insemination timing, and corrective interventions.

Purpose of Developing Web and Android Software

The aim of developing this softwares is to provide an accurate, accessible tool for predicting and monitoring heat stress in dairy cows. It is available in both web (Shiny App) and Android versions to ensure usability in different conditions (on the farm or in the office). The software supports fast and informed decision-making by automatically calculating multiple thermal indices, classifying stress levels, and displaying results visually. It is also designed to allow future enhancements such as smart alerts and real-time data integration.

Thermal Indices Used

The software uses several indices to monitor and assess thermal stress in dairy cows. These indices estimate the thermal load on the animal's body by combining environmental data. The main indices used are:

THI (Temperature-Humidity Index)

THI is one of the most widely used indices for evaluating thermal stress in dairy cows. It combines ambient temperature and relative humidity to indicate the heat stress imposed on the dairy cows. To interpret THI values, the software uses the following clear and simple classification:

THI \leq 55 = No Risk; 56 \leq THI \leq 67 = Low Risk; THI \geq 68 = High Risk

Adjusted THI (THI_{adj})

This is an enhanced version of THI that, in addition to temperature and humidity, incorporates other environmental factors such as wind speed and solar radiation. It offers more accurate results under real-world environmental conditions, making it especially suitable for farms significantly affected by weather fluctuations.

ETIC (Equivalent Temperature Index for Cattle)

ETIC is one of the most comprehensive indices for assessing thermal comfort in dairy cows. It estimates the animal's effective body temperature by considering four key environmental variables: temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation.

Web-Based Software Development (Shiny App)

Tools and Framework

To develop the web version of the thermal stress monitoring software, the R programming language and the open-source Shiny package were used. Shiny was selected due to its simplicity, flexibility, and the ability to integrate statistical analysis with interactive user interfaces efficiently.

Application Structure

The application includes three main components:

Input: Data received via API (temperature, humidity, wind speed, solar radiation)

Processing: Internal calculation of thermal indices

Output: Display of categorized results through tables, graphs, and color-coded stress levels

Key Features:

- User selection of location and real-time display of meteorological data (temperature, humidity, wind speed, solar radiation)
- Access to various thermal stress indices (THI, THI_{adj}, and ETIC) and THI classification
- 5-day forecasting capabilities
- Online deployment via "shinyapps.io", no installation needed
- Fast, cost-effective development
- Usable by researchers, consultants, and farm managers

Access to the Web-Based Application

<https://animalanalyzer.shinyapps.io/heatguard/>

Android Software Development

Development Environment

To enhance usability in dairy farm, an Android version of the software was created using Android Studio. This version allows users to operate the software independently of a computer and directly on mobile devices. The interface was designed to be simple, readable, and responsive for quick interpretation of results.

Software Name and Version

Heat Guard, Version 1.0.0

Key features include:

- User-defined location input with real-time meteorological data (temperature, humidity, wind speed, solar radiation)
- Access to various heat stress indices including THI, THI_{adj}, and ETIC, along with THI classification
- 5-day weather forecasts
- Fully online access via shinyapps.io (no installation required)
- Fast, low-cost development with wide usability for researchers, consultants, and farm managers

Access link: <https://animalanalyzer.shinyapps.io/heatguard/> (below)

This evaluation is conducted using R software and is currently in its initial phase. The program is being carried out under the supervision of Professor Atzori and his colleagues at the University of Sassari. (04042025)

City name:

Metric	Value
City	Sassari
Temperature	20.88 °C
Humidity	53 %
Wind Speed	2.04 m/s
Solar Radiation	0 W/m ²

Heat Stress Indices

Heat.Stress.Index	Value
THI-NRC	66.59
THI _{adj}	66.98
ETIC	13.59

5-Day Heat Stress Forecast

day	avg_temp	avg_humidity	avg_wind	avg_solar	THI_NRC	THI_ADJ	ETIC
Tuesday	27.77	54.88	2.58	0.00	76.04	75.33	20.39
Wednesday	28.29	52.38	2.54	0.00	76.40	75.76	20.70
Thursday	27.64	53.62	2.73	0.00	75.69	74.67	20.01
Friday	26.51	56.75	2.98	0.00	74.55	73.05	18.93
Saturday	20.73	89.00	2.07	0.00	68.63	69.00	16.24

Android Application Development

To increase practical usability on dairy farms, a standalone Android version was developed using Android Studio.

Main capabilities:

- Real-time weather data via API with user-selected location
- On-device calculation of THI, THI_adj, and ETIC
- Visual heat stress levels using color-coded risk categories
- 5-day forecast functionality to support proactive decision-making

Heat Guard

Enter City Name
Sassari

Fetch Data

Metric	Value
Temperature	24.88 °C
Humidity	33.0 %
Wind Speed	1.51 m/s
Solar Radiation	1.9000000000000001 W/m ²
Heat Stress Index	Value
THI-NRC	69.86
THIadj	71.28
ETIC	16.31

Heat Stress Level: High Risk

Home Forecast About

Heat Guard

Enter city name
Sassari

Fetch Forecast

5-Day Heat Forecast

Day	T	H	Wind	Solar	THI	Adj	ETIC
2025-5-19	23.3	44.0	1.9	6.5	69.0	69.7	15.4
2025-5-20	19.7	63.1	4.5	6.6	65.6	61.2	10.4
2025-5-21	18.4	77.0	5.4	4.0	64.2	57.9	8.7
2025-5-22	16.9	76.9	4.3	8.1	61.8	57.8	8.1
2025-5-23	16.7	67.0	4.8	5.5	61.3	56.2	6.5

Home Forecast About

Heat Guard

Heat Guard – Version 1.0.0

This application was developed under the supervision of Professor Atzori and his research team at the University of Sassari.

It is currently under active development and improvement.

Home Forecast About

D) Development of the Heat Guard Chatbot Using Zephyr

Definition of the Heat Guard Chatbot

The Heat Guard chatbot is an intelligent, interactive tool specifically designed to answer questions related to heat stress in dairy cows. Developed using modern machine learning, semantic search, and large language model (LLM) technologies, the chatbot aims to provide farmers, consultants, and researchers with quick and reliable access to scientific information in this domain.

Importance and Purpose of the Chatbot in Heat Stress Management

Given the complexity and volume of information related to heat stress, using a chatbot allows users to obtain accurate, scientific, and relevant answers in a short time. Chatbots can play an essential role in training, rapid decision-making, and environmental risk assessment in dairy farms.

The goal of developing the Heat Guard chatbot is to provide an accurate, scalable, and user-friendly solution that can be utilized in both research and on-farm settings. The chatbot is hosted online via Hugging Face Spaces, requiring no installation for users.

Structure and Development

Data Preparation (Semantic Search)

To implement semantic search, scientific texts and related documentation (particularly regarding heat stress) were divided into small segments or "chunks." Using the SentenceTransformer model "all-MiniLM-L6-v2", an embedding vector was generated for each chunk. The output was saved in a CSV file.

Coding

In this stage, the CSV file was loaded and converted into a NumPy array. A FAISS index was created for vector-based search. For each user query, the top 3 most relevant text chunks were retrieved and used to construct a structured prompt for the Zephyr-7B model. This prompt was then sent to the model through the Hugging Face API. The chatbot's graphical interface was built using Gradio.

Preparing the Space Runtime Environment

The files were uploaded to Hugging Face Spaces for deployment and execution of the chatbot.

Features and Capabilities

- Provides expert-level answers to questions related to heat stress in dairy cows
- Uses the Zephyr-7B language model to generate accurate, science-based responses
- Offers a clean, intuitive, and interactive interface built with Gradio

Access and Usage

Chatbot Access URL:

<https://animalanalyzer-heatguard.hf.space/>

Conclusion and Future Outlook

Performance Evaluation

The Heat Guard chatbot demonstrates strong performance in delivering scientific and accurate answers while maintaining a smooth user experience.

Future Development Plans

- Adding multilingual support
- Connecting to external scientific databases for real-time, up-to-date responses
- Expanding the knowledge base to cover broader aspects of dairy cattle management
- Developing a mobile version and integrating it with the existing Heat Guard Android application

Figure 1. Web interface of the Heat Guard chatbot.